

ORGANIZATION AND MANAGEMENT OF CORPORATIONS

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Abstract. This article is devoted to the study of the processes of organization and management of corporations. Corporate structures are an important part of organizing a modern economy, and their success depends on strategic management planning, effective allocation of resources, and stability of management systems. The legal and regulatory aspects of the organization of corporations and management principles are widely discussed in the article.

Key words : Corporation, management, organization, strategy, corporate structure, management, stakeholders, sustainable development, legal and regulatory requirements, efficiency.

A corporation is a developed large [shareholder](#) society, a set of legal and physical entities organized for a specific activity. A corporation may also unite citizens in the same profession or field of activity. It appeared in the middle of the 20th century. The current market economy has a key position in all sectors of the economy in developed countries. Joint-stock companies form the basis of corporations. From the second half of the 19th century, international corporations developed widely. In most cases, corporations combine the main producers of the same products, resulting in monopolization of production. At the same time, the corporation supports the centralization of investment capital, provides scientific and technical progress, product competitiveness and longevity. According to the status of ownership, it is divided into state, private, mixed (joint) corporations, industry, [agriculture](#) , [transport](#) , [communication](#) and other types of corporations. In developed countries, there are many cases where industries are organized into corporations.

Establishing a corporation usually involves a number of legal and economic steps. Initially, the corporate structure is chosen, in this process the form of the enterprise, legal

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status, governing bodies and financial plans are determined. Corporations, such as a joint-stock company, have the status of a legal entity and raise capital through shares. One of the most important aspects of establishing a corporation is its legal liability, which maintains a legal distance between the company and its shareholders. It is also important to comply with regulatory requirements such as tax, labor laws and government controls.

Since a corporation is an independent legal entity, its property, assets and liabilities are not owned by shareholders or management, but by itself. It works on the principle of legal independence.

Shareholders of a corporation are its owners, but they are liable only to the extent of the capital (shares) they have contributed to the corporation. For example, if a corporation goes into debt and experiences financial difficulty, shareholders may only lose their investment, but their personal assets will not be at risk. Therefore, the personal assets of the shareholders are not related to the liabilities of the corporation.

The main goal of corporate management is to optimally allocate resources, coordinate employee activities and implement long-term growth strategies through effective management of the organization. Among the most common management models, centralized and decentralized management structures are distinguished. The board of shareholders and top managers play an important role in corporate governance. They must set the company's strategy and coordinate the interests of stakeholders, including shareholders, customers, employees, and society.

One of the most important aspects of corporate governance is strategic planning. This process includes setting long-term goals of the corporation, increasing competitiveness and strengthening its position in the market. A sustainable development strategy is becoming increasingly important for corporations, as the demand for increased economic efficiency while taking into account social and environmental responsibility is increasing.

A corporation may purchase, own, and manage property, but that property is owned directly by the corporation itself, not by shareholders or management. Shareholders cannot directly control the property or assets of the corporation; their profits are limited to dividends or income from the value of the shares.

Shareholder benefits are usually limited to **dividends** or **increases in stock value** , but when a corporation earns a profit, some of that profit can be used in other ways to continue its operations without being distributed to shareholders. The rest of the income remains at the disposal of the corporation and is used in the following ways:

1. Investing in production and growth :

A corporation may allocate a portion of its income to development and expansion. This includes investing in new projects, upgrading technologies, developing new markets or developing new products. These investments can increase the value of the corporation in the future and provide long-term benefits to shareholders.

2. Storage of reserves (reserve funds):

Corporations usually allocate a portion of earnings to a reserve fund. This amount is needed to prepare the corporation for unexpected financial difficulties or market changes. These reserves ensure the financial stability of the company and help in dangerous situations.

3. Debt repayment:

If a corporation has debts, the corporation can use a portion of its income to pay off the debts. This will reduce the financial burden of the company and make it possible to get more profit in the future.

4. Buyback of shares:

In some cases, corporations decide to repurchase their shares on the open market. This method helps to increase the share price as the number of shares in the market decreases. As a result, shareholders benefit from an increase in share price.

Corporation	Sector	Market cap(in USD)
1. Apple	Technology	\$2.776 trillion
2. Microsoft	Technology	\$2.558 trillion
3. Saudi Aramco	Oil & Gas	\$2.138 trillion
4. Alphabet	Technology	\$1.601 trillion
5. Amazon	E-commerce	\$1.426 trillion

6. Nyidia	Technology	\$1.074 trillion
7. Meta Platforms	Social Media	\$798.89 trillion
8. Berkshire Hathaway	Diversified Investments	\$761.65 trillion
9. Tesla	Automatic	\$694.62 trillion

There are the top 9 corporations in the world market and their market share in 2023. In the first place, we can see Apple Corporation, which is engaged in the production of technology products as its main sector, with a market share of \$2.776 trillion in 2023. Corporations such as Microsoft, Saudi Aramco, Alphabet (Google), and Amazon are ranked after Apple.

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